

THE IMPORTANCE OF A DESCRIPTIVE DICTIONARY IN INDEPENDENT LEARNING OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Аннотация: *Статья посвящена изучению значения описательного словаря в самостоятельном изучении иностранного языка. Даны некоторые методические рекомендации самостоятельных исследований.*

Annotation: *The article is devoted to study the importance of a descriptive dictionary in independent learning of a foreign language. There given some methodical recommendations of independent studies.*

Ключевые слова: *Упражнения, повторение, определенных действий развития, навыки, умений, словарь*

Key words: *Exercises, repetition, certain development actions, skills, abilities, vocabulary*

Vocabulary plays an important role in teaching foreign languages. Vocabulary materials also have their own difficulties in teaching vocabulary. Because the word is a very complex and multifaceted phenomenon. Each word is known to have a certain meaning and usage. The size of the meaning of a word, the variety of meanings of a word, the ability of the same word to combine with other words, the use of a word is related to the size of its meaning and is determined by the specific circumstances at the time. Pronunciation is also difficult.

One of the most important principles when creating a dictionary is that it is known that the meaning of a word is correct, and the meaning of this principle is provided along with alternative versions of a word in a translation dictionary. The value and importance of any vocabulary is measured to the extent that stylistic advice for keywords is provided along with keyword alternatives, and when are specific words defined stylistically? where? to whom? The style should represent a world of relative application. This is especially important when compiling bilingual dictionaries.

Teaching independent work and taking an interest in raising the level of skills and abilities are also important for practical mastery of foreign languages. This is

because a student must master the skills and abilities of independent work so that the knowledge acquired in the future cannot be forgotten. Therefore, a foreign language helps to shape precisely these qualities of a person in a new society.

Teaching a foreign language is an important skill for an educated person like L.V. This skill is formed primarily in the course of analytical reading, which is an essential part of learning to read a foreign language at a high level.

Independent work on texts, native language translations, and many other exercises contributed to the formation of disruptive behaviors for students to overcome difficulties. Because the language materials in textbooks are in foreign languages, you often have to work on your own. The text uses a dictionary to decipher the meaning of unfamiliar words found in exercises and homework. It's natural. You can also solve this problem by using a descriptive dictionary. As the translation of the text gives you ideas for unfamiliar words, the possibilities of searching for synonyms and finding the necessary alternatives expand. The content of the text is stylistically correct and the translation is closer to the original. A multilingual dictionary with explanations helps students effectively use existing knowledge in addition to language skills and abilities, as well as enhance their logical observation and scientific potential. Therefore, it is not an exaggeration to say that the descriptive dictionary forms the ability to work independently in teaching foreign languages.

Psychologists recognize that because thoughts arise through speech, the human child assimilates through speech the experiences accumulated by human society. Words represent concepts as units of language. A set of words in a language forms a vocabulary as a system. Words have an emotional (external) side and a spiritual (internal) side. The term "emotional" means that the word is "provocative". Through fear and hearing, we can see (read) and hear (hear and understand). We can speak (using the movements of our hands) and write through the movements of our words. You can see or hear words as they are spelled or spoken. When we say this word inwardly (spiritually) we mean content and understanding. Meaning refers to a connection to something or the event it represents.

A concept is a form of thinking that reflects the essential characteristics of things and events. Concepts are formed through logical techniques such as comparison, analysis, abstraction, synthesis, and generalization. For example, in Spanish, English, German, French, Persian and Russian, the concept of "white" is expressed as a word in the form "blanco, white, weiB, blanc, safed, white". The expressed concept is one and the word is seven. Any word if not a term. Can't

mean more than that. "White" has different meanings, such as white paper, white plaster, whitewash.

Refine the meaning of a concept by using a picture in the Picture Dictionary to represent the concept. When learning new words, concepts, pictures and words from the language are combined in the mind, i.e. associative connections, and words are mastered in multiple languages, improving the student's foreign language vocabulary. Psychologists distinguish five types of associations.

1. Similarity (synonym)
2. Inverse meaning (antonym)
3. Equally related. Example: tables, chairs (furniture)
4. Expansion of meaning, dining furniture, apples.
5. Interdependent disease death (cause and effect) military force (part of the whole) chit cotton picker

The words provided in the descriptive dictionary may also be presented in thematic and alphanumeric format. As you learn vocabulary, it is easy to memorize words, close and paste dictionaries, make sentences, make letters, talk with words, and have conversations with your interlocutors using picture dictionaries on a variety of topics.

From the above, we can conclude that visual dictionaries also play an important role in improving the vocabulary of foreign language learners. Questions about lexicographic principles also play an important role in lexicography. The first is to determine the purpose and function of the dictionary, the second to scientifically substantiate the vocabulary in the dictionary, the third to place keywords, the fourth to select the items corresponding to the dictionary entries, Fifth is to be clear. The meaning of the word, the sixth is the example, and the seventh is the style. Grammar, etymology and other indicators, translation of the ninth dictionary.

The importance of explanatory dictionaries in language education is enormous. This is because when students learn words in a foreign language, looking at the images makes them easier to remember and learn. In this regard, it is worth mentioning the English-German subject Uzbek explanatory dictionary "It is better to see once than to hear a thousand times" by Mukhtorkhon Umarkhojaev. It is worth noting that the selection of topics in the dictionary, the active use of thematic vocabulary in everyday communication, the selection of appropriate pictures that reveal the meaning of words and, finally, their availability as an additional resource in any educational institution. German and English lessons.

The level of scientific and practical study of the above principles is a key factor in improving the quality of any dictionary.

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